

1 GRANULAR FLOWS IN FLUID

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18 1 INTRODUCTION

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20 Avalanches, landslides, and debris flows are geophysical hazards, which involve rapid
21 mass movement of granular solids, water, and air. Globally, landslides cause billions of
22 pounds in damage, and thousands of deaths and injuries each year. Hence, it is important to
23 understand the triggering mechanism and the evolution of flow. The momentum transfer
24 between the discrete and continuous phases significantly affects the dynamics of the flow
25 as a whole.¹ Although certain macroscopic models are able to capture simple mechanical
26 behaviours,² the complex physical mechanisms occurring at the grain scale, such as
27 hydrodynamic instabilities, formation of clusters, collapse, and transport,¹ have largely
28 been ignored. In particular, when the solid phase reaches a high volume fraction, the strong
29 heterogeneity arising from the contact forces between the grains, and the hydrodynamic
30 forces, are difficult to integrate into the homogenization process involving global
31 averages.¹ In order to describe the mechanism of immersed granular flows, it is important
32 to consider both the dynamics of the solid phase and the role of the ambient fluid.³ The
33 dynamics of the solid phase alone are insufficient to describe the mechanism of granular
34 flow in a fluid; it is important to consider the effect of hydrodynamic forces that reduce the
35 weight of the solids inducing a transition from dense-compacted to dense-suspended flows,
36 and the drag interactions which counteract the movement of the solids.⁴ Transient regimes
37 characterized by change in solid fraction, dilation at the onset of flow and development of
38 excess pore pressure, result in altering the balance between the stress carried by the fluid
39 and that carried by the grains, thereby changing the overall behaviour of the flow.³ In the
40 present study, 2D Lattice-Boltzmann and Discrete Element Method is adopted to capture
41 the fluid-soil interactions in underwater avalanches.
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44 2 LBM-DEM Formulation

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46 The Lattice Boltzmann equation Method (LBM) is an alternative approach to the classical
47 Navier-Stokes solvers for fluid flow and works on an equidistant grid of cells, called lattice
48 cells, which interact only with their direct neighbors.⁵ The fluid domain is divided into a
49 rectangular grid or lattice, with the same spacing 'h' in both the x- and the y-directions, as
50 shown in Figure 1. The present study focuses on 2-D problems; hence, the D2Q9

51 momentum discretization is adopted, where the fluid particles at each node are allowed to
 52 move to their eight intermediate neighbors with eight different velocities \mathbf{e}_i ($i = 1, \dots, 8$).⁶
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 56 **Figure 1** The Lattice Boltzmann discretization and D2Q9 scheme: (a) a standard LB
 57 lattice; (b) D2Q9 model
 58

59 The nine discrete velocity vectors are defined as:
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$$61 \quad \begin{cases} e_0 = (0, 0) \\ e_1 = C(1, 0); e_2 = C(0, 1); e_3 = C(-1, 0); e_4 = C(0, -1); \\ e_5 = C(1, 1); e_6 = C(-1, 1); e_7 = C(-1, -1); e_8 = C(1, -1); \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

62
 63 in which C is the lattice speed ($=h/\Delta t$). Where, Δt is the discrete time step. The primary
 64 variables in the Lattice Boltzmann formulation are called the fluid density distribution
 65 functions, f_i , each relating the portable amount of fluid particles moving with the velocity
 66 \mathbf{e}_i along the i^{th} direction at each node. The macroscopic variables can be obtained from the
 67 particle distribution functions, according to:
 68

$$69 \quad \rho = \sum_{i=0}^{\beta-1} f_i \quad (\text{macroscopic fluid density}) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{u} = \frac{1}{\rho} \sum_{i=0}^{\beta-1} f_i \mathbf{e}_i \quad (\text{macroscopic velocity}) \quad (2)$$

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 71 where, $i \in [0, \beta-1]$ is an index spanning the discretized momentum space. There are nine
 72 fluid density distribution functions, f_i ($i = 0, \dots, 8$), associated with each node in the
 73 D2Q9 model. This simple equation allows us to pass from the discrete microscopic
 74 velocities that comprise the LBM back to a continuum of macroscopic velocities
 75 representing the fluid's motion. The BGK (Bhatnagar-Gross-Krook) approximation is used
 76 to describe the streaming and the collision of the particles. Streaming and collision (i.e.,
 77 relaxation to local equilibrium) is defined as:
 78

$$79 \quad f_i(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{e}_i \Delta t, t + \Delta t) = f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) - \frac{1}{\tau} [f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) - f_i^{eq}(\mathbf{x}, t)] \quad (i = 0, \dots, 8) \quad (3)$$

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 81 where, $f_i(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{e}_i \Delta t, t + \Delta t) = f_i(\mathbf{x}, t)$ describes the streaming part and the collision part,
 82 which brings the system to local equilibrium is described by $\frac{1}{\tau} [f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) - f_i^{eq}(\mathbf{x}, t)]$. τ is a
 83 non-dimensional relaxation time parameter, which is related to the fluid viscosity.
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85 **2.1 LBM-DEM Coupling**

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87 Lattice Boltzmann approach can accommodate large grain sizes and the interaction
88 between the fluid and the moving grains can be modelled through relatively simple fluid –
89 grain interface treatments. Further, employing the Discrete Element Method (DEM) to
90 account for the grain – grain interaction naturally leads to a combined LB – DEM
91 procedure.⁷ The Eulerian nature of the LBM formulation, together with the common
92 explicit time step scheme of both LBM and DEM makes this coupling strategy an efficient
93 numerical procedure for the simulation of grain – fluid systems. Such a coupled
94 methodology is used in simulating grain – fluid systems dominated by grain – fluid and
95 grain – grain interactions. To capture the actual physical behavior of the fluid – grain
96 system, it is essential to model the boundary condition between the fluid and the grain as a
97 non-slip boundary condition, i.e. the fluid near the grain should have similar velocity as the
98 grain boundary. The solid grains inside the fluid are represented by lattice nodes. The
99 discrete nature of lattice, results in a stepwise representation of the surfaces, which are
100 circular, hence sufficiently small lattice spacing is adopted.

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102 **2.2 Permeability**

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104 In DEM, the grain – grain interaction is described based on the contact interactions. In a
105 3D granular assembly, the pore spaces between grains are interconnected, whereas in 2-D
106 assembly, the grains are in contact with each other that result in a non-interconnected pore-
107 fluid space. This results in a no flow condition in a 2-D case. In order to overcome this
108 difficulty, a reduction in radius is assumed only during LBM computations (fluid and fluid
109 – solid interaction). The reduction in radius allows interconnected pore space through
110 which the surrounding fluid can flow (reduced $R=0.7r$ to $0.95r$, ‘ r ’ is grain radius). The
111 reduction in radius is assumed only during LBM computations, hence this technique has no
112 effect on the grain – grain interactions computed using DEM. Different permeability can
113 be obtained, for any given initial packing, by varying the reduction in the radius for the
114 grains, without changing the actual granular packing. Cumulative β method is adopted to
115 generate a randomly packed granular assembly with a polydispersity of 1.8 (see Figure 2).⁸
116 The size of the grains varies between 1.25mm to 2.2mm.

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119 **Figure 2** (a) Randomly packed sample generated by cumulative β method; (b) PSD Curve

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121 A square sample of 50 mm x 50 mm is used to determine the transverse permeability.
122 Dirichlet boundary condition,⁹ i.e. pressure/density constrain is applied at the left and the
123 right boundaries. A small increment ($10^{-4} \rho_0$) in density is applied at the left hand side
124 boundary and a constant density is maintained at the right hand side boundary. This results
125 in a gradient of pressure causing the fluid in the domain to flow. The mean velocity of flow
126 (v) is determined and the permeability of the sample (k) is computed as:

127

$$128 \quad k = v \cdot \mu \cdot \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta P} \quad (4)$$

129

130 where μ is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid (Pa.s), Δx is the thickness of the bed of
131 porous medium (m), and ΔP is the applied pressure difference (Pa). In the present study,
132 the radius is varied from 0.7 to 0.95 to obtain a wide range of permeability for the sample.
133 Increase in the size of the grain from 0.7 to 0.95 reduces the porosity from 0.60 to 0.27.
134 The permeability computed from LB – DEM method is verified by comparing it with an
135 analytical solution. One of the widely used analytical solutions for permeability is the
136 Carman – Kozeny equation (i.e. the CK Model), which is based on Poiseuille flow through
137 pipe and is mainly used for 3D, homogenous, isotropic, granular porous media at moderate
138 porosities. In the present study, a modified Carman – Kozeny equation that takes into
139 account the microstructure of the fibers and is valid in a wide range of porosities is
140 adopted.¹⁰ The normalized permeability is defined as:

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$$142 \quad \frac{k}{d^2} = \frac{\varepsilon^3}{\psi_{CK} (1-\varepsilon)^2} \quad (5)$$

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148 **Figure 3** (a) Variation of flow rate for different reduction in radius, (b) Permeability vs.
149 porosity

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151 In the CK model, the hydraulic diameter D_h , is expressed as a function of measurable
152 quantities porosity and specific surface area.

$$154 \quad D_h = \frac{4\varepsilon V}{S_v} = \frac{\varepsilon d}{(1-\varepsilon)}; \text{ with } a_v = \frac{\text{particle surface}}{\text{particle volume}} = \frac{S_v}{(1-\varepsilon)V} = \frac{4}{d} \quad (6)$$

155
156 With the total wetted surface, S_v , and the specific surface area, a_v . The above value of a_v is
157 for circles (cylinders) – for spheres $a_v=6/d$. ψ_{CK} is the empirically measured CK factor,
158 which represents both the shape factor and the deviation of flow direction from that in a
159 duct. It is approximated for randomly packed beds of spherical grains. The variation in the
160 flow rate for different reduction in radius is presented in Figure 3a. The normalized
161 permeability for different porosity obtained by varying the radius from 0.7 to 0.95 is
162 presented in Figure 3b.

163 It can be observed from the figure that the permeability decreases drastically as the
164 radius is varied from 0.7r to 0.95r. The granular assembly is almost impermeable for a
165 radius of 0.95r. The normalized permeability is found to match the qualitative trend of the
166 Carman-Kozeny equations. The LB – DEM permeability curve lies between the
167 permeability curves for spherical and cylindrical grain arrangements implying a better
168 approximation of permeability in 2D granular assembly by reducing the radius during
169 LBM computations.

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3 GRANULAR AVALANCHES IN FLUID

In this section, we study the behavior of immersed granular avalanches for different permeability. We consider 2D poly-disperse system ($d_{\max}/d_{\min}=1.8$) of circular discs in fluid. The simulations were carried out with 1000 grains of density 2650 kg/m^3 and a contact friction angle of 26° . The collapse of the column was simulated inside a fluid with a density of 1000 kg/m^3 and a kinematic viscosity of $1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. The choice of a 2D geometry has the advantage of cheaper computational effort than a 3D case, making it feasible to simulate very large systems with an important number of nodes for a reasonable computing time. A granular column of aspect ratio ‘a’ of 0.8 was considered. Radius of the grains was varied from $0.7r$ to $0.95r$ during LBM computations. Dry and buoyant analyses were done to compare the effect of hydrodynamic forces on the run-out distance.

The final run-out profile for a reduced grain size of $0.7r$ and $0.95r$ are presented in Figure 4. The less permeable column collapses further, while the highly permeable column entraps more water and has smaller run-out distance. The rheology of the flow tends to change, with change in permeability. Figure 5a presents the evolution of normalized run-out distance for different permeability conditions. Normalized time is defined as $\sqrt{H/g}$,¹¹ where, H is the height of the granular column and g is acceleration due to gravity. It can be observed from the figure that the dry and buoyant columns run farther and evolve quicker than the immersed case. The run-out is found to increase with decrease in permeability. The time required for the flow to initialize increases with decrease in permeability, i.e. a highly permeable column collapse quicker in comparison to a less permeable granular column. Three distinct regimes can be observed in the immersed avalanche, similar to the observations in dry granular column collapse:¹¹ (1) a vertical-fall regime, where the grains located at the top undergo vertical falls and the grains at the bottom are ejected horizontally by the fluid; (2) a heap regime, where the grains at the top move along an inclined stationary deposit; (3) a horizontal regime, where the grains move essentially horizontally. In this last regime, fluid re-circulations were observed leading to the formation of vortex flows, which moves towards the surface (see Figure 4). Figure 5b depicts the evolution of kinetic energy for low ($R=0.95r$ and $\eta=0.25$) and high ($R=0.7r$ and $\eta=0.6$) permeable granular columns. The collapse of granular pile in fluid takes longer to initialize in comparison with dry and buoyant collapse. Similar to the dry granular column collapse, the run-out distance for collapse in fluid is proportional to $\sqrt{KE_{\max}}$. Where, KE_{\max} is the maximum kinetic energy observed during the flow.

(a)

(b)

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Figure 4 Final run-out profile for reduction in radius of (a) $0.7r$ and (b) $0.95r$

(a) Evolution of run-out

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(b) Evolution of kinetic energy

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Figure 5 Effect of permeability on the flow dynamics

219 4 SUMMARY

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221 In this work, we have studied the behavior of immersed granular avalanches using LB –
222 DEM approach. In 2D immersed column collapse simulation, the radius of the grains is
223 reduced during LBM computations to allow fluid to flow through the pore-space, which is
224 otherwise not interconnected. By reducing the radius of grains during LBM computations,
225 different permeability can be achieved for the same initial packing. Immersed granular
226 avalanches are significantly affected by hydrodynamic forces. Development of a negative
227 pore pressure postpones the onset of avalanche. The run-out distance is found to be
228 significantly affected by the permeability, the run-out distance is found to increase with
229 decrease in permeability. Further research will be carried out to study the effect of relative
230 density on the evolution of immersed granular avalanches.

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237 **References**

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